

IMPROVED TRANSDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE
FOR EFFECTIVE ECOSYSTEM-BASED
MARITIME SPATIAL PLANNING AND
CONSERVATION IN EUROPEAN SEAS

Deliverable D7.4 Final Report

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MARINEPLAN PROJECT SUMMARY

The diversity of terrestrial and marine life is dramatically affected by human interventions including climate change. Compelling and growing evidence shows that biodiversity underpins ecosystem functions and services, and consequently, human benefits depend on them. Thus, the importance of ecosystems in a good state cannot be underestimated and calls for an effective management of marine activities and sustainable use of marine and coastal resources.

Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) is the main governance process that ideally balances economic, ecological and socio-cultural goals through the regulation of human uses at sea. As a future-oriented process, MSP is well-placed to realise sustainable marine futures. With global and regional conservation and green energy targets ahead, there is an urgent need to define pathways for a better alignment of MSP and systematic conservation planning, as part of the operationalisation of an Ecosystem-Based approach to MSP (EB-MSP).

The EU-funded MarinePlan project supported the implementation of EB-MSP through the development of a Decision Support System (DSS). It offered guidance for an improved alignment of MSP, spatial conservation, and restoration interventions during the challenging times of ever-increasing pressures on marine ecosystems.

This main goal was achieved through four specific objectives for the European seas:

- #1 Co-develop with stakeholders the conceptual elements of the DSS (guidelines and tools) and derive best practice guidance for EB-MSP implementation.
- #2 Develop quantitative metrics to operationalise Ecologically or Biologically Significant marine Area (EBSA) criteria and their application at various spatio-temporal scales.
- #3 Implement and apply the DSS based on objectives #1 and #2, its guidelines, metrics, and tools at Planning Sites representing the diversity of European marine areas.
- #4 Provide recommendations and improvements concerning the shortcomings, impediments to, and opportunities of prevailing governance processes to enhance the implementation of EB-MSP.

MarinePlan developed and applied the EB-MSP DSS within seven Work Packages and eight European Planning Sites. The Planning Sites ranged from coastal ecosystems to open ocean and the deep sea and from local to transboundary scales. Applying and validating the DSS incorporated realistic planning scenarios, key action points to achieve the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and policy recommendations on how to enhance EB-MSP implementation in European Seas. MarinePlan has and will continue to communicate results to decision-makers at horizontal (between sectors) and vertical (from local to European) levels and further enable the transfer of knowledge to areas in differing socio-ecological settings. The improved natural and social science base ensures effective policymaking to support a greater coherence in implementing environmental policies as well as to enable streamlined planning for marine industries.

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1 AIM OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable reports the main activities and achievements of MarinePlan in months 25 through 36 of the project (10/2024 – 09/2025). It gives an overview over the main events, achievements and publications. The aim is to inform stakeholders and funders about the project’s progress and completion.

1.1 CONTRIBUTORS

Table 1. Names and roles of contributors to this deliverable.

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2 INTRODUCTION & MAIN EVENTS

MarinePlan started officially on the 1st of October 2022 and ended on the 30th of September 2025. A consortium of 17 partners from the EU, UK and Canada have been working together over the past 36 months to improve transdisciplinary science for effective ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning and conservation in European Seas. MarinePlan has developed several EB-MSP and prioritization tools as well as refining and applying 3D and 2D drift models. Additionally, the EB-MSP DSS has already been implemented within seven Work Packages and eight European Planning Sites. During the final year of the project (months 25-36) we have focused on maintaining our solid foundation of internal communication and frequent exchange between partners, fulfilling MarinePlan's objectives of co-development with stakeholders and ensuring the implementing of the DSS at the different Planning Sites. The cornerstone of the final 12 months of the project was the development of scenario-based EB-MSP planning options. All PS implemented realistic planning scenarios reflecting their specific objectives, and some PS also implemented hypothetical scenarios. These planning scenarios were pivotal in identifying common knowledge gaps and challenges in EB-MSP processes. They also provide recommendations and key action points to support effective EB-MSP implementation with a particular focus on achieving the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 targets of protecting 30% of European seas, with 10% under strict protection.

The third and final Planning Site Workshop was held from April 8th-10th, 2025 in Hamburg, Germany. During the meeting, the Planning Site team gathered with the main goals of i) identifying the challenges in applying the DSS at the PS, ii) establishing a guideline for building and testing the scenarios, and iii) contrasting PS scenario outputs with existing MSP processes in order to identify knowledge gaps and develop bespoke policy recommendations.

On September 29th and 30th, 2025, all partners from the MarinePlan consortium, an Advisory Board member, and just over 140 online participants from 36 different countries gathered online for the MarinePlan Final Event. Here, the MarinePlan team introduced the project and background, which led into introducing the MarinePlan Decision Support System (DSS). Then each of the DSS building blocks (e.g., the MarinePlan EB-MSP assessment tool, policy and stakeholder analyses, EBSAs and how they drive coherent conservation planning, and building 2030-30%-10% scenarios in European Seas) was presented in greater detail. To illustrate how the DSS functions as a whole and the process of developing scenarios, 3 Planning Sites were showcased and presented in detail their site characteristics, how they defined their site-specific conservation objectives, and what solutions they reached. Work package 4 presented the StoryMaps and pathways of impact, as well as the policy recommendations for each PS. During the second part of the meeting, various tools and programs developed within MarinePlan were presented as tutorials: the EB-MSP assessment tool, operationalising EBSA criteria for ecosystem-based conservation and management, integrating drift modelling with ecological connectivity in the Southern North Sea, communicating ecosystem change and health with OceanViz, marine heatwaves across depths, and three toolsets (Prior3D, PriorCON, and PriorOECMs). Connections between the WPs, PSs, and our main objectives were also showcased, as well as how MarinePlan plans to influence and advise policy on multiple levels.

As a means of illustrating the intricacies and details of how the various DSS building blocks interact to developing an effective EB-MSP and conservation in European Seas, MarinePlan, with the help of graphic design company Illuteam, develop a series of infographics that detail each foundational block in the process and show how they interact. These infographics were shared with everyone at the MarinePlan Final Event, and will be added to the project website.

Main overview infographic detailing the building blocks of a Decision Support System; developed in WP7 for dissemination and publication on the project website.

3 MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS BY WORK PACKAGE

Work Package 1: EB-MSP knowledge and guidance

Work Package 1 has completed all of their Tasks, and all seven Milestones for WP1 have been achieved. In the final 12 months of the project, the remaining Milestone 1.7: Internal workshop with MarinePlan Planning Sites leaders to get final feedback and lessons learnt on the implementation of the EB-MSP framework, has been met in January 2025. All WP1 Deliverables are completed, with D1.2: ‘A best practice guide for the implementation of D1.2 EB-MSP in European Seas’ being delivered in the final year of the project.

During the final reporting period, the EB-MSP framework and tool were iteratively improved through several online and face-to-face meetings. This involve rewording the task/actions based on the feedback received by PS leaders, and subsequent operationalisation of the EB-MSP assessment framework and DSS into a publicly available web app tool, which facilitates its use in ongoing MSP initiatives and guides the assessment of already adopted Marine Spatial Plans (MSP) (i.e., in total, 636 users from 56 countries have accessed the app in July 2024-June 2025 period). In January 2025, the process for developing the EB-MSP framework and tool (based on a comprehensive literature review and co-development with experts) was published in Communications Earth and Environment.

PS leaders were also provided with a concise document detailing MarinePlan’s context and objectives, along with in-depth explanations of the EB-MSP framework. This was intended to facilitate communication with their respective MSP practitioners and competent authorities, enabling them to either complete the full EB-MSP assessment with them or receive feedback on their responses. In February 2025, a meeting with PS leaders was held to get final feedback on the implementation of the

EB-MSP framework (M1.7), and the final EB-MSP assessment results were presented to the Planning Sites at the 3rd PS Workshop in April 2025.

At a subsequent meeting in May 2025, the development of D1.2: 'Best practice guide for the implementation of EB-MSP in European Seas' was discussed, and a template was created where MarinePlan partners collated (i) detailed descriptions of each of the 130 task/actions that compose the EB-MSP assessment framework, (ii) information about the approaches, tools and methods used at their PS that could be used for the implementation of EB-MSP, (iii) guidance and recommendations towards the implementation of each of the statements, and (iv) useful information and/or links to pertinent documents and scientific publications that could be used by future users of the tool both during the development of their marine spatial plans, and at the adaptive management stage to improve the implementation level of the tasks and/or actions. This was organized with information from the literature to create the basis for the good practice examples for the implementation of EB-MSP in European Seas (D1.2; final version submitted in July 2025). To maximise outreach of the good practice EB-MSP guide, all information has been uploaded to the publicly available EB-MSP tool, and an additional functionality has been added so users can filter their results tailored to their planning unit. This provides users their information in a downloadable spreadsheet.

Screenshot of the EB-MSP Assessment Tool video on YouTube.

Work Package 1 results and outcomes (and in particular the developed EB-MSP framework and tool) were promoted and disseminated during the final 12 months of the project via several presentations at specialized conferences (e.g., ICES Annual Science Conference, XVIII International Symposium on Oceanography of the Bay of Biscay, EU-MSP week, 11th Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) World conference) and the development of a video introducing EB-MSP, as well as a tutorial on the use of the EB-MSP tool. Both videos were published to the MarinePlan website and also on YouTube.

Sub- infographic detailing the EB-MSP Assessment Framework building block of the Decision Support System.

The EB-MSP tool was also presented to the international OCTO Community, reaching 120 international experts in MSP implementation. The EB-MSP tool has a dedicated section on the EU MSP platform, which ensures its delivery to European experts in MSP, and at the ‘MSPGlobal International Guide on Marine/Maritime Spatial Planning’ published in 2025 by IOC-UNESCO and the European Commission. Additionally, the work carried out within WP1 has been periodically communicated to the general audience through several articles in national, European, and international media, radio interviews, and posts on X and LinkedIn. During the MarinePlan Final Event in September 2025, a live tutorial showcased the EB-MSP tool and all its functions and applications.

All of the above-mentioned steps taken and progress made towards the development and implementation of the tools relate directly to Objective 3 of the MarinePlan project.

Work Package 2: Science-based EBSA and MPA network design

Work Package 2 has completed all the Milestones set, and has completed all three Deliverables outlined in their work package. Deliverable 2.3: ‘Report on physical connectivity between areas of significant ecological value’ was completed and submitted during the final reporting period.

Before the Planning Sites could develop scenarios and planning options, a robust science base for the prioritisation and zonation of MPA networks was needed. In line with this, Task 2.2- ‘Evaluation of physical oceanographic datasets required for assessing EBSA criteria’ was completed and formed the foundation for subsequent drift modelling experiments. The spatial distribution of existing and newly developed EBSA criteria was measured, and under WP2, developed (i) spatially explicit, quantitative metrics for EBSA criteria that are compatible with ecosystem-based, environmental state indicators (e.g., MSFD), (ii) guidance for the application of these metrics at various spatial scales, and (iii) the quantification of dispersal and movement corridors across different life stages (functional connectivity), biodiversity attributes, and species interactions. Assessing the spatial connectivity between marine protected areas (MPAs), WP2 also proposed spatially efficient zonation and how to avoid competing sea uses where possible. In the last reporting period, the remaining EBSA criterion

were established and quantitatively linked to population- and ecosystem dynamics which, in turn, may affect the capacity to supply marine ecosystem services.

Through the developed EBSA metrics, WP2 considered the different temporal and spatial scales and explicitly addressed the linkages and connectivity between identified hot spots of biodiversity attributes, and already designated MPAs and EBSAs to effectively address conservation and restoration priorities while accounting for the effects of climate change. In line with their Objectives and completion of Task 2.3, WP2 built on the setup achieved in the first 24 months of the project by further refining and applying the 3D and 2D drift models at the PSs. The 3D and 2D drift models each have a different focus on connectivity: the 3D approach covers conditions where vertical movement is critical (such as in deeper waters) and focuses on source and sink areas, whereas the simpler 2D approach investigates the long-term temporal variability in horizontal transport by ocean currents.

Under WP2, MarinePlan measured temporal dynamics and connectivity relevant to the EBSA criteria, in particular in view of climate change. New measures have been developed where necessary (such as regional extinction risk or predicted changes in productivity rates under warming environments), as conditions for the analyses on trade-offs of planning options. Temporal dynamics were considered by investigating variability in connectivity among MPAs at different temporal and spatial scales, including structural and functional connectivity, climatic velocity, the identification of ecological corridors and hot spots, and spillover from MPAs. In the final 12 months of the project, the connectivity analyses were fitted to the specific requirements of each PS depending on data availability in the different Planning Sites. Case-by-case meetings were held to negotiate planning site needs, computational feasibility, and tool-related requirements. Both modelling approaches provided tailor-made connectivity data that were then used by the R-software packages developed in WP3.

Additional progress in the reporting period includes extending the simulations to multi-seasonal cycles, validating cross-boundary exchange statistics, and finalizing routines for travel times, arrival times, and residence times. The outputs directly feed into EBSA-based assessments and underpin the scenario development in WP3 and WP5.

Sub- infographic detailing the EBSA & Connectivity building block of the Decision Support System.

During the MarinePlan Final Event in September 2025, a live tutorial showcased the EB-MSP tool and all its functions and applications.

All of the above-mentioned steps taken and progress made in WP2 relate directly to Objective 2 of the MarinePlan project.

Work Package 3: Prioritisation tools and scenario development

Much progress was made during months 25-36 of the MarinePlan project in the tasks set out for Work Package 3. All Tasks were successfully completed, and all deliverables were delivered.

As a result of the three workshops held last year which addressed Task 3.2: Developing MarinePlan decision tools for integrated planning and prioritization of sites in EB-MSP, Task 3.2 was completed with the delivery of D3.2 and presented a suite of decision-support tools (DSTs) for integrated conservation planning and the expansion of MPA networks. Over the last 12 months, WP3 has also developed several new tools in keeping with Task 3.2 and Objective 3 of the MarinePlan Project.

The tools developed and tested include: prior3D for three-dimensional prioritisation across depth gradients (already completed during the first 18 months of the project); priorCON for connectivity-based community detection and network design; a corridor-identification methodology based on evolutionary game theory; approaches for integrating subsurface marine heatwave data into climate-smart planning; priorOECMs - a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis tool for assessing OECMs; the Coastal Fishing Pressure Index to capture small-scale fisheries impacts; point process models to improve species distribution estimates in data-poor regions; a 4D planning framework combining spatial and temporal dimensions to incorporate climatic risk; a framework for integrating biological invasions into prioritisation; and an inventory of alternative cost layers to account for socio-economic trade-offs.

All tools were designed to be modular and adaptable across ecological, social, and policy contexts, and were tested in selected planning sites to ensure operational relevance. The participatory process remained central, with input from the three thematic workshops feeding directly into the refinement of the tools. Collectively, the outputs of Task 3.2 provide a comprehensive and flexible toolkit that strengthens ecosystem-based marine spatial planning by enabling robust consideration of biodiversity objectives, socio-economic factors, and climate-related challenges.

Additionally, Task 3.3 was successfully completed, resulting in Deliverable 3.3. Building on the groundwork laid in the first 18 months, a comprehensive scenario analysis was undertaken to explore plausible futures for marine biodiversity conservation and maritime spatial planning up until 2030. The process involved six methodological steps: specification of objectives, identification and prioritisation of drivers through expert consultation (85 responses worldwide), framing of contrasting driver states, development of four detailed scenarios, and translation of these scenarios into planning options for the MarinePlan Planning Sites.

Presentation slide from the MarinePlan Final Event introducing some of the tools developed during MarinePlan and example placement of where they can be used in the DSS process.

Two key drivers were prioritised—climate change and international politics/governance—each framed into contrasting states, forming the basis of four scenarios: Climate Apocalypse, Battles and Breaths, Peaceful Collapse, and Sustainable Harmony. Each scenario was analysed under the 10-tenets framework (ecological, technological, economic, political, social, administrative, legislative, cultural, ethical, communicative), highlighting the diverse challenges, opportunities, and bottlenecks in meeting the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 targets.

A set of plain-language factsheets was produced to communicate the scenarios effectively to diverse stakeholders, thereby supporting participatory planning and decision-making. Further, the scenarios were operationalised through planning options tailored to MarinePlan Planning Sites, supported by advanced decision-support tools (e.g., prior3D, priorCON, MCDA for OECMs) and two alternative integration frameworks for combining biodiversity, connectivity, and cost data. An additional “realistic” planning option was also developed to bridge global scenarios with site-specific contexts. Finally, Task 3.3 introduced Bow-Tie Analysis as a complementary risk management approach to assess scenario consequences, integrating the DAPSI(W)R(M) framework. This structured methodology enhances the capacity of ecosystem-based MSP to anticipate risks, identify preventive and mitigative measures, and ensure adaptive and robust planning outcomes.

Together, these outputs provide a robust methodological and practical foundation for scenario-based conservation planning, ensuring that MarinePlan contributes directly to advancing ecosystem-based MSP and achieving the EU Biodiversity Strategy’s 2030 targets.

Sub- infographic detailing the Spatial Planning Scenarios building block of the Decision Support System.

All of the above-mentioned steps taken and progress made in WP3 towards the development and implementation of the tools relate directly to Objectives 1, 3 and 4 of the MarinePlan project.

Work Package 4: Policy advice and stakeholder engagement

During the final 12 months of the MarinePlan project, all Tasks, Deliverables and Milestones were completed. Specifically, Task 4.2 and T4.3, Deliverable 4.3, and the final two Milestones (hosting the Policy Roundtable and creating the StoryMaps).

Initially, WP4 planned to host an in-person back-casting workshop at MarinePlan’s final meeting to develop policy recommendations to improve the science-base for EB-MSP (Task 4.3). However, as the Final Event was hosted online (encouraging not only EU and national policy makers to attend, but also interested attendees from around the world), the policy recommendations were developed by taking the findings of each Planning Site (related to institutional landscapes and the opportunities/barriers to achieving governance targets (e.g., 30x30 conservation goal)) and embedding them in bespoke ArcGIS StoryMaps. The StoryMaps, which were translated to local languages, were shared with a broad range of identified stakeholders in each Planning Site. During the last year of the project, WP4 created tailored policy briefs for each of the 8 Planning Sites, detailing the trade-offs between incentives, job creation, regulations and resources conservation needs. Examples of these tailored policy briefs as well as QR codes for each brief were showcased and presented at the MarinePlan Final Event online in September 2025.

Sub- infographic detailing the Stakeholders and Governance building block of the Decision Support System.

All of the above-mentioned steps taken and progress made in WP4 relate directly to Objective 4 of the MarinePlan project.

Work Package 5: Planning Sites and Communication

All of the Tasks, Deliverables and Milestones for WP 5 have been delivered and reached by the end of month 36. Specifically, Task 5.3: Testing and refining tools, concepts and scenarios, was completed, and Deliverables 5.1 and 5.2 were delivered.

The third and final Planning Site Workshop was held from April 8th-10th, 2025 in Hamburg, Germany. During the meeting, the Planning Site team gathered with the main goals of i) identifying the challenges in applying the DSS at the PS, ii) establishing a guideline for building and testing the scenarios, and iii) contrasting PS scenario outputs with existing MSP processes in order to identify knowledge gaps and develop bespoke policy recommendations.

Deliverable 5.1, synthesizing results across PSs concerning EB-MSP and SCP status and obstacles, was previously submitted in April 2024, and then revised according to the recommendations made by the reviewers at/after the project's review meeting in May 2024. It was subsequently resubmitted in October 2024. It has been discussed that a paper will be written from D5.1, detailing potential gaps in current EB-MSP practices as well as pathways of integrating EB-MSP and SCP.

Deliverable 5.2, which incorporates the work done from tasks 5.3 and 5.4 was completed in the final reporting period. This deliverable synthesizes the development and application of scenario-based Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) across eight Planning Sites (PS) ranging from sub-national to transboundary scales. The deliverable provides an overview of realistic and hypothetical planning scenarios and identifies common knowledge gaps and challenges in EB-MSP processes. Deliverable 5.2 helped to inform WP4's policy recommendations and key action points to support effective EB-MSP implementation with a particular focus on achieving the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 targets of protecting 30% of European seas, with 10% under strict protection.

All of the above-mentioned steps taken and progress made in WP5 relate directly to all Objectives of the MarinePlan project.

Work Package 6: Data Management and visualisation tools for EB-MSP

The tasks in WP6 were open until the end of the project, with updates, revisions and additions being made throughout the life of the MarinePlan project. By the end of month 36, all Tasks, Deliverables and Milestones have been delivered and reached. In the last 12 months specifically, WP6 completed

Illustrating change over time with OceanViz in WP6.

M6.4 and M6.5 with some training courses extending past deadlines due to demand. Deliverable 6.1 was submitted and revised as per the review report following the reviewers' recommendations and resubmitted October 2024. D6.1 was resubmitted under the title 'Preliminary Data Management Plan'. The new DMP was designated as D6.5 and the new delivery date was amended to Month 36 to better support the Consortium throughout the duration of MarinePlan. Deliverables 6.2, 6.3, 6.4, and 6.5 were all submitted within the last 12 months of the project.

Additionally, in the final 12 months of the project, WP6 has ensured correct and systematic use of the MarinePlan data inventory, SharePoint document storage, pCloud data storage, and the deployment of data and deliverables on Zenodo. The WP6 team has also been steadily debugging

and extending both the Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) and OceanViz approaches. Specifically, several bugs were fixed in the EwE software, and several preview releases of EwE version 6.7 were issued over the duration of the MarinePlan project, accrediting MarinePlan. The OceanViz source code was first released to the public on GitHub at the end of 2024 (<https://github.com/Official-EwE/oceanviz/>), and work has continued to date to visualize the Western Mediterranean case study.

Work Package 6 assisted MarinePlan partners in deploying data to Zenodo in compliance with FAIR principles, adhering to the Zenodo templates for both data and deliverables. In the past 18 months, EII has also co-organized another annual EwE modelling course at the Institute of Marine Sciences (ICM-CSIC) in Barcelona under the umbrella of 6 EU and Spanish projects, including MarinePlan.

All of the above-mentioned steps taken and progress made in WP6 indirectly contributed to the achievement of all MarinePlan Objectives (1-4), as well as achieving the three outcomes of MarinePlan.

Work Package 7: Project Management and Dissemination

By Month 36, all Tasks, Deliverables and Milestones have been delivered and reached.

The Tasks completed (T7.1 - T7.3) were continuously updated until the end of the project. In accordance with Task 7.1, for example, WP7 continually and frequently exchanged information with our sister projects as well as other outside projects, organized meetings and workshops (i.e., joint conferences and/or presentations), and maintained internal reporting throughout the duration of the project. (NOTE: specific conferences, workshops, and communication and dissemination accomplishments can be found in Table 5.1, Appendix 1, below). Under T7.2, WP7 continuously maintained our internal and external communication tools (e.g., SharePoint for internal sharing and joint work on documents, pCloud for data sharing, Zenodo community as the project repository, and updated templates for meeting minutes, presentations, etc.).

Dissemination of MarinePlan under Task 7.3 continues to be ongoing even after the official end of the project. The project's social media and online presence has been kept up to date, with all presentations and tutorials from the Final Event in September 2025 being added to the MarinePlan website. In the final 12 months, an additional project flyer and two additional posters were developed and added to our website. As a side note, in the last reporting period MarinePlan decided to switch from using the platform X to using BlueSky, so our followers and post counts are lower than they would have been if we had continued to use X. MarinePlan also joined the Marine Protected Area-Connectivity Network (MPA-CN), an umbrella initiative developed to centralise and connect MPA-related projects across Europe, as well as fostering collaboration among MPA managers, stakeholders, and conservation experts. It serves as a central one-stop shop for MPA-related projects, promoting collaboration and information exchange.

As previously mentioned, the intricacies and details of how the various DSS building blocks interact to developing an effective EB-MSP and conservation in European Seas was detailed in a series of infographics produced for MarinePlan by the graphics company Illuteam. These infographics were showcased at the MarinePlan Final Event, and will be added to the project website.

Milestone 7.8: Final Symposium was reached at the end of Month 36 in the form of the MarinePlan Final Event. The Final Event was hosted online and split over two consecutive afternoons, from the 29th to the 30th September, 2025. An online webinar was created and the registration link shared within the consortium, to the PSs and their stakeholder contacts, the EU MSP Platform, in the Marine Protected Area- Connectivity Network (MPA-CN) newsletter, as well as being posted on our website

and social media channels. The event was open for everyone to join, and such a wide distribution of the registration link yielded over 230 registrants from 36 different countries.

This Final Event encouraged marine spatial planners, stakeholders, policy and decision makers, industry managers, experts in marine conservation and sustainability, and the scientific community to come together and learn about MarinePlan's improved and innovative transdisciplinary approach to effective ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning (EB-MSP) and conservation in European seas. In the first afternoon of the event, we explored the elements of marine conservation planning that are necessary for an ecosystem-based approach, Decision Support System (DSS) building blocks, and real examples of scenarios and lessons learned from our Planning Sites. The second afternoon featured tutorials and training on the use of the tools and programs developed in MarinePlan and examples of their implementation. All presentations and tutorials were uploaded to the MarinePlan website for public access.

WP7 has contributed to the achievement of MarinePlan objectives, as well as achieving all outcomes of MarinePlan (see Figure 1) by facilitating project management, coordination, communication (internal and external) and dissemination.

Figure 1: Linkages between expected outcomes, deliverables, tasks and objectives completed during the MarinePlan Project; checked circles indicate completed.

3.1 DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION & COMMUNICATION (DEC) MEASURES

In Table 3.1 we show the progress made during the lifetime of the MarinePlan project (36 months), by providing the status of the different success indicator measures, which correspond to the defined Dissemination & Exploitation & Communication (DEC) measures.

Table 3.1: Status assessment of the defined success indicators and measures which correspond to the defined Dissemination & Exploitation & Communication (DEC) measures.

Target group / Audience	Channels, tools and materials used and timeframe / regularity (How?) and Measure of success	Timeframe for completion	Total target	Achievement during month 25-36	Objective(s) fulfilled
General public	Project website	ongoing	1	Done; www.marineplan.eu	
General public	Short introductory videos	beginning of project	few	2 Completed; https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VIM0jrcoe4g , https://e.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=kZoj2UZ4kCyuzMJg4yYyUC9pU5CeXxPR5XV	
General public	Podcasts	beginning of project, regular	10	Not completed (due to capacity limitations & questions about impact/relevance) 2 Radio Interviews given	
General public	Social media	ongoing		ongoing BlueSky posts; 36 followers by month 36 (left X and went to BlueSky)	
General public	Press releases	beginning of project, regular	3	Azores news contribution of MarinePlan annual meeting: https://www.rtp.pt/play/p56/e716215/telejornal-acores ; start 15:06 min	
General public	Project flyer(s)	beginning of project	1	Decided against flyer for sustainability reasons and made a poster and a roll-up banner to present the project. 2 project leaflets made.	
General public	Newsletters	regular	6	Not completed due to capacity limitations	
General public	Newspaper/magazine articles	regular, conclusion and summary	3	3 Press releases, 20 Media articles	
Scientific community (research and education)	Peer-reviewed publications	regular	20+	19 published in final 12 months of project, several in preparation	1-4
Scientific community (research and education)	Presentations at EU and international symposia and conferences	regular	10	25 presentations	1-4

Scientific community (research and education)	Public Deliverable Reports	regular	15	13 (will be published as soon as approved by EU)	1-4
Scientific community (research and education)	Workshops/Trainings	regular	3	4 hosted, 3 contributed/participated	1-3
Scientific community (research and education)	The approach of peer review by appropriate scientific communities will ensure quality standards	regular		Ongoing for all scientific publications	
Scientific community (research and education)	The website will provide links to publications, reports etc.	regular		Ongoing; www.marineplan.eu	
Scientific community (research and education)	Final project symposium	conclusion and summary	1 (100+ attendees)	Completed; over 230 registrants from 36 countries, about 140 attendees (day of)	1-4
Policy makers & NGOs	Reports, policy briefs & "factsheets" detailing the trade-offs between incentives, job creation, regulations and resources conservation needs	regular, conclusion and summary	11	8 completed (one for each PS)	4
Policy makers & NGOs	Website summaries of key MarinePlan research linked to specific policy areas	conclusion and summary		n.a.	4
Policy makers & NGOs	Direct input to national, regional, European and international advisory bodies,	regular		Participation in workshops, conferences and including representatives in events of the project - WP3 high level stakeholder workshops	

	including ICES, GFCM, STECF, FAO, OSPAR and HELCOM				
Policy makers & NGOs	Descriptions of Planning Site scenarios demonstrating improved MPA spatial models and EB-MSP options	regular, conclusion and summary	8		D5.1, D1.1: are the foundations for the scenario development
Policy makers & NGOs	Policy roundtable with policymakers from across the EU to co-develop MSP recommendations	conclusion and summary	1		n.a.
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Articles in industry magazines and on websites	regular	2		
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Specific pages on the project website	ongoing			Links to technical reports and publications are provided on the website
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Stakeholder engagement workshops (online and in person) per Planning Site	regular	24 (3x8 PS)		Ongoing regular meetings with stakeholders; For examples the Bay of Biscay: Workshop for D1.1
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Specific information material designed to present relevant MarinePlan results refined for each site with opportunities	regular			Each PS will use the general MarinePlan templates to present project results; further general findings are continuously updated in a general project presentation

	for feedback and co-development				
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	EB-MSP DSS with best practice guidance	conclusion and summary	1		Completed; see WP1
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Operational EBSA criteria for MPA designation	conclusion and summary			Completed; see WP2
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Regionalised runs of drift models	conclusion and summary			Completed; see WP2
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Spatial optimisation tools	conclusion and summary			Completed; see WP3
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Visualisation tools to analyse trade-offs	conclusion and summary			Completed; see WP1, WP3; WP6 (OceanViz)
policy-makers, MSP practitioners, conservation practitioners, industry representatives	Training courses (physical and web-based) at Planning Sites specific tools and training for the EB-MSP DSS provided for each Planning Site	regular, conclusion and summary	3		WP3: 5 Workshops completed

4 PUBLICATIONS

1. Bas, M., Ortega Cerdà, M., Castro Cadenas, M. D., Lloret Lloret, E., Steenbeek, J., Ramírez Benítez, F., ... & Coll, M. (2024). Impactos acumulativos y planificación marítima. Los proyectos GES4SEAS y MARINEPLAN. Primeros resultados.
<https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/358206>
2. Castro-Cadenas, M. D., M. Barreiros, M. Bas, M. Ortega-Cerdà, J. Claudet, M. Coll and V. Sbragaglia (2025). Fishing activities within Spanish marine protected areas in the Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Policy* 177: 106686.
<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2025.106686>
3. Doxa, A., Adam, C., Nagkoulis, N., Mazaris, A., Katsanevakis, S. (2025). prior3D: An R package for three-dimensional conservation prioritization. *Ecological Modelling*, Vol. 499, (110919).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2024.110919>
4. Elliott, M., Borja, A., Cormier, R. (2025). Managing marine resources sustainably- But how do we know when marine management has been successful? *Ocean and Coastal Management*, Vol. 265, (107623).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2025.107623>
5. Elliott, M., Kennish, M.J. (2024). Chapter 6.1. A Synthesis of Anthropogenic Impacts and Solutions in Estuarine and Coastal Environments. Volume 6, *Treatise on Estuarine & Coastal Sciences*, 2nd Edition., Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp 1-56.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/referencework/9780323910422/treatise-on-estuarine-and-coastal-science-second-edition>
6. Galparsoro, I., et al. (2025). Assessment tool addresses implementation challenges of ecosystem-based management principles in marine spatial planning processes. *Communications Earth & Environment*, Nature.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s43247-024-01975-7>
7. Giakoumi, S., Richardson, A., Doxa, A., et al. (2025). Advances in systematic conservation planning to meet global biodiversity goals. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 40:1.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2024.12.002>
8. Jung, M., M. Coll, A. Metaxas, S. M. Thomas, K. Tsuchiya, B. Oliveira, A. Popp and M. Rounsevell (2025). Expansion of conservation areas should be informed by sectoral interlinkages. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*. (Accepted)
9. Konsta, K., Doxa, A., Katsanevakis, S., Mazaris, A. (2025). Projected marine heatwaves over the Mediterranean Sea and the network of marine protected areas: a three-dimensional assessment. *Climatic Change*, 178:17.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-025-03860-4>
10. Lukyanova, O., Pouso, S., García-Barón, I., Borja, A., Bas, M., Cormier, R., Katsanevakis, S., Neuenfeldt, S., Stelzenmüller, V., Galparsoro, I. (2025). Operationalising Ecologically or

Biologically Significant Marine Areas criteria for ecosystem-based conservation and management: The Bay of Biscay case. *Biological Conservation*, 308.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2025.111156>

11. Nagkoulis, N., Adam, C., Mamoutos, I., Katsanevakis, S., Mazaris, A. (2024). An Ecological Connectivity dataset for Black Sea obtained from Sea Currents. *Data in Brief*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.111268>

12. Nagkoulis, N., Papazekou, M., Katsanevakis, S., Mazaris, A. (2024). Spatial conservation planning: Proposing clustering methods to improve connectivity protection. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 00:1-11.

<https://besjournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/2041-210X.14459>

13. Pennino, G. M., J. P. Zurano, M. Hidalgo, A. Esteban, C. Veloy, J. M. Bellido and M. Coll (2024). Spatial patterns of β -diversity under cumulative pressures in the Western Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Environmental Research* 195(106347).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2024.106347>

14. Petza D., Amorim E., Ben Lamine E., et al. (2024). Assessing the potential of Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures (OECMs) for contributing to conservation targets: A global scoping review protocol. *Open Res Europe*, 3:118

<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16116.3>

15. Petza, D., and Katsanevakis, S. (2024). Science-informed recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of area-based fisheries management for fisheries sustainability and marine conservation: A global mini-review. *Fisheries Research* Vol. 272 (106947).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2024.106947>

16. Queirós, A., et al. (2025). The opportunity for climate action through climate-smart Marine Spatial Planning. *npj Ocean Sustainability*, 4:26.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s44183-025-00129-2>

17. Rehren, J., Kruse, M., Probst, W., Gordo-Vilaseca, C., Lemmen, C., Krishna, S., Stelzenmüller, V. (2025). Future cumulative effects on demersal fish in a transforming North Sea pressure landscape. *Journal of Environmental Management*. 392 (126727).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126727>

18. Steenbeek, J. (2024). Doctoral Thesis. Ecosystem modelling for the ocean decade- facing the challenges.

<https://upcommons.upc.edu/handle/2117/417801>

19. Stranga, Y., Mazaris, A., and Katsanevakis, S. (2024). Protected Mediterranean invertebrates: The known and the unknown. *Biological Conservation*, Vol. 297 (110740).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2024.110740>

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

During months 25-36 of the MarinePlan project, much has happened in the way of communicating and disseminating the project and our achievements. Audiences include research communities, industry and business partners, innovators, EU institutions, national, regional, and local authorities, civil society, citizens, specific end user communities, international authorities (such as the UN, OECO, etc.), and investors. Communication and dissemination included activities such as giving talks and presentations (e.g., at conferences or conventions) about the MarinePlan project and our objectives, poster presentations, further education and training (e.g., lectures or seminars), and social media activities such as posts on X (and later BlueSky) and involvement with the scientific community online.

All of these activities, including details on time and place, type of dissemination, target audience, and more, can be found in Table 5.1, in Appendix 1.

Some partners have also taken on MSc or PhD students to fulfil human capacity building activities. These activities are also included in Table 5.1, Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1

Table 5.1. MarinePlan Dissemination and Communication Activities from 10/2024 until 09/2025.

<u>Lead Participating Organization</u>	<u>Type of Activity</u>	<u>Type of Action</u>	<u>Activity Name</u>	<u>Description of Objective(s) with Reference to Specific output</u>	<u>MAIN Target Audience</u>
CSIC	Dissemination	Education and training events	Open Doors Days – Science Week ICM-CSIC: Adapting to change!	Our goal in participating in this Open Doors Day – Science Week event with the activity “Adapting to Change!” is to raise awareness about how marine species respond to environmental changes. Through interactive and engaging experiences, we aim to bring science closer to the public and highlight the importance of research in understanding and protecting our oceans in a changing world — and the crucial role of effective management of Marine Protected Areas.	Public
CSIC	Dissemination	Other	Post in X channel by the @iMARES_group profile	The goal of this post is to raise awareness about the @MarinePlanEBMSP project and its objectives, highlighting the importance of marine planning. Through the video, it aims to inform and educate the audience about how improving marine planning benefits both people and the environment. It also mentions @ICMCSIC to link the collaboration and promote the content. https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1848641134458703929	Research communities
CSIC	Dissemination	Education and training events	Activity with children in the Casal de Barri de la Verneda (Barcelona): Adapting to change!	The objective of this activity was to raise awareness among participants about the importance of protecting marine ecosystems, particularly through the management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). The little explorers had the opportunity to learn about the roles of scientists and environmental managers, promoting awareness of environmental conservation and biodiversity.	Public
CSIC	Dissemination	Other	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @ima-res-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post was to highlight the Antarctic adventure that took place last Friday at CBarri de la Verneda, where participants learned about managing Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). It aimed to engage young explorers by teaching them the importance of ecosystem protection and allowing them to step into the roles of scientists and environmental managers. https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1894029499211100287	Public

CSIC	Dissemination	Other	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post is to announce the publication of a new paper in *Communications Earth & Environment*, highlighting the development of a tool to assess ecosystem-based marine planning. The tool was tested on marine plans from Spain and France, with the aim of improving governance and sustainability in marine management. The post encourages readers to access and read the full paper. https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1884914517924008263 https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3lgxceiu6ak2l	Research communities
CSIC	Dissemination	Other	Post in BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of this post is to share the team's participation in the 3rd Mediterranean MSP workshop organized by the European MSP Platform. It highlights the discussion on the involvement of maritime sectors in marine conservation and MSP as a framework for a sustainable Blue Economy. https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3lgvamx7t5s26	Research communities
CSIC	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	MED-MSP-CoP: 3rd Mediterranean Workshop for the preparation of a recommendation paper	To contribute to the discussion on Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) and its role in marine conservation and the sustainability of the Blue Economy. Through this workshop, the aim was to share knowledge and experiences on the involvement of maritime sectors in conservation, as well as to promote the use of MSP as a tool to achieve a more sustainable future for marine activities.	Research communities
CSIC	Communication	Press release	A new tool promotes the sustainable development of maritime sectors and marine biodiversity conservation	The press release announces the launch of an innovative digital tool led by AZTI and developed in collaboration with ICM-CSIC, within the framework of the MarinePlan project. This tool facilitates the evaluation of the sustainability of maritime activities in relation to marine biodiversity. https://www.icm.csic.es/en/news/new-tool-promotes-sustainable-development-maritime-sectors-and-marine-biodiversity	Research communities
UAEGEAN	Dissemination	Other	Use of the MarinePlan tools prior3D and priorCON in designing the Ionian National Marine Park (Greece).		National authorities
UAEGEAN	Communication	Social media	Bluesky post about MarinePlan paper	The press release announces the launch of an innovative digital tool led by AZTI and developed in collaboration with ICM-CSIC, within the framework of the MarinePlan project. This tool facilitates the evaluation of the sustainability of maritime activities in relation to marine biodiversity.	Research communities
UAEGEAN	Communication	Social media	Bluesky post about MarinePlan paper	The objective of this post was to communicate the MarinePlan publication "Advances in systematic conservation planning to meet global biodiversity goals"	Research communities
UAEGEAN	Communication	Social media	Bluesky post about MarinePlan paper	The objective of this post was to communicate the MarinePlan publication "An ecological connectivity dataset for Black Sea obtained from sea currents"	Research communities

UAEGEAN	Communication	Social media	Bluesky post about MarinePlan paper	The objective of this post was to communicate the MarinePlan publication "prior3D: An R package for three-dimensional conservation prioritization"	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Interview	Radio interview on the EB-MSP assessment tool	The objective of this interview in Onda Cero was to communicate to the general audience the relevance of ecosystem-based marine spatial planning when dealing with the sustainability of human activities at sea (https://www.ondacero.es/emisoras/pais-vasco/san-sebastian/m%C3%A1s-de-uno-gipuzkoa/mas-uno-gipuzkoa-05022025_2025020567a3660e0b2ad20001b4bfb2.html)	Research communities
AZTI	Dissemination	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Attendance to the EU-MSP week	Invited to attend as an expert to the event	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Video	Video tutorial on the use of the EB-MSP assessment tool	The video describes in a synthetic way how to use the tool and how to extract information from the assessment	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Video	Video introducing ecosystem-based marine spatial planning	The video describes for the general public what is the ecosystem-based marine spatial planning and why it is important to develop new spatial plans according to ecosystem-based management principles	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	Leaflet of MarinePlan project	Leaflet distributed during the EU-MSP week to show the main objectives of MarinePlan project	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	Leaflet of EB-MSP assessment tool	The leaflet introduces the EB-MSP assessment tool and how it can be implemented	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Exhibition	MarinePlan exhibition in EU-MSP week	An exhibition desk on the EU-MSP conference with leaflets, screen and roll-up	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	TV/Radio campaign	Radio interview on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Interview in the Españoles en la Mar radio programme. An interview about ecosystem-based management and its relevance for the sustainable management of human activities at sea (https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/espanoles-en-la-mar/espanoles-mar-ciencias-oceanicas-para-conseguir-planeta-sano/16460665/)	Research communities
UNINA	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	54 th Congress of the Italian Society of Marine Biology	The objective of the contribution to this congress is to present the results of the Scoping Review on Systematic Conservation Planning carried out within Task 3.1	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in basque referring to the development of the EB-MSP tool (https://zientziakaiera.eus/2025/02/09/asteon-zientzia-begi-bistan-519/)	Research communities

AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish where the EB-MSP tool its presented and its role towards sustainability (https://www.ecoticias.com/sostenibilidad/eb-msp-assessment-tool-herramienta-sectores-maritimos-biodiversidad-marina)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article on a US-webpage presenting the EB-MSP tool, where it is explained its potential application for the sustainable management of fisheries (https://www.seafoodsource.com/news/environment-sustainability/ifco-announces-2-4-billion-shipments-of-groceries-in-its-reusable-packaging-worldwide-in-2024-new-azti-tool-standardizes-ecosystem-based-marine-planning)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in basque referring to the development of the EB-MSP tool and its potential role in the sustainable development of human activities (https://aldizkaria.elhuyar.eus/albisteak/itsas-sektoreen-garapen-jasangarria-sustatzeko-tre/)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in basque referring to the development of the EB-MSP tool and its potential role in the sustainable development of human activities (https://zientzia.eus/artikuluak/itsas-sektoreen-garapen-jasangarria-sustatzeko-tre/)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article on a UK-webpage presenting the EB-MSP tool and its role in the promotion of marine biodiversity conservation is presented (https://envirotecmagazine.com/2025/02/05/new-tool-will-promote-marine-biodiversity-conservation/)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article on an Australian webpage presenting the EB-MSP tool and and its potential role in the sustainable development of human activities (https://blueconomynews.earth/azti-researchers-develop-tool-for-ecosystem-based-marine-spatial-planning/)	Investors
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article on an Italian webpage presenting the EB-MSP tool and and its potential role in the sustainable development of human activities (https://www.pesceinrete.com/pianificazione-spaziale-marina-una-nuova-frontiera-per-la-sostenibilita/)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish where the EB-MSP tool its presented and its role towards the sustainable development of maritime activities and conservation (https://www.msn.com/es-es/noticias/tecnologia/azti-coordina-una-herramienta-que-promueve-el-desarrollo-sostenible-de-los-sectores-mar%C3%ADtimos-y-la-conservaci%C3%B3n/ar-AA1ynIzD)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish where the EB-MSP tool its presented and its role towards sustainability and international collaboration (https://www.diariomaritimo.com/especiales/litoral/nueva-herramienta-para-la-planificaci%C3%B3n-espacial-marina-promueve-la-sostenibilidad-y-la-colaboraci%C3%B3n-internacional)	Research communities

AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article on a US-webpage presenting the EB-MSP tool and its role for the sustainable development of maritime sectors (https://ecomagazine.com/news/coastal/a-new-tool-promotes-the-sustainable-development-of-maritime-sectors/)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish where the EB-MSP tool its presented and its role towards marine biodiversity conservation (https://www.naucher.com/azti-coordina-una-herramienta-para-la-conservacion-de-la-biodiversidad-marina/)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article on a Irish webpage presenting the EB-MSP tool and its role towards marine management and biodiversity conservation (https://thefishingdaily.com/science-and-research/tool-enhances-marine-management-and-biodiversity-conservation/)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article on a Irish webpage presenting the EB-MSP tool and its role for sustainable marine development (https://thefishsite.com/articles/azti-announces-framework-for-sustainable-marine-development)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish where the EB-MSP tool its presented and its role for the sustainable development of maritime activities (https://www.energias-renovables.com/energias_del_mar/investigadores-vascos-disean-un-metodo-para-compatibilizar-20250204)	Industry, business partners
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in basque referring to the development of the EB-MSP tool and its role in sustainable development (https://www.noticiasdegipuzkoa.eus/sociedad/2025/02/04/azti-desarrolla-herramienta-promover-gestion-9236394.html)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish referring to the development of the EB-MSP tool and its role in the sustainable development of maritime activities and conservation (https://www.lavanguardia.com/local/paisvasco/20250204/10349911/azti-coordina-herramienta-promueve-desarrollo-sostenible-sectores-maritimos-conservacion-agenciaslv20250204.html)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish referring to the development of the EB-MSP tool and its role in the sustainable development of maritime activities and conservation (http://www.gentedigital.es/san-sebastian/noticia/3995582/azti-coordina-una-herramienta-que-promueve-el-desarrollo-sostenible-de-los-sectores-maritimos-y-la-conservacion/)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Media article	Media article on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Media article in spanish referring to the development of the EB-MSP tool and its role in the sustainable development of maritime activities and conservation (https://www.europapress.es/euskadi/noticia-azti-coordina-herramienta-promueve-desarrollo-sostenible-sectores-maritimos-conservacion-20250204110706.html)	Research communities

AZTI	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Online event for the International OCTO Community	Presenting the EB-MSP tool to the International OCTO Community (https://octogroup.org/assessing-the-alignment-of-ecosystem-based-management-principles-in-marine-spatial-planning/)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Website	EB-MSP assessment tool announcement in the EU MSP platform	https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/practices/assessment-tool-addresses-implementation-challenges-ecosystem-based-management	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Other	EB-MSP assessment tool	Erasmus Mundus master class in Marine Environment and Resources master (https://www.ehu.eus/en/web/master/master-marine-environment-resources)	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Conference session organisation: Navigating tomorrow's seas through integrative ecosystem service assessments and decision-support tools". 11th Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP) World conference. Darwin (Australia). 23-27 June 2025.	Presentation of different decision support tools	Research communities
AZTI	Communication	Conferences	Virtual poster at One Ocean Science Congress	Lukyanova, O., Pouso, S., García-Barón, I., Borja, A., Bas, M., Cormier, R., Katsanevakis, S., Neuenfeldt, S., Stelzenmüller, V., and Galparsoro, I.: Operationalising Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Area Criteria for Ecosystem-Based Conservation and Management: The Bay of Biscay Case, One Ocean Science Congress 2025, Nice, France, 3–6 Jun 2025, OOS2025-961, https://doi.org/10.5194/oos2025-961 , 2025.	Research communities
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post is to announce our participation in the 3rd Planning Site Workshop celebrated in Hamburg. https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1909558299239870871 https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3lmccbcosww2f	Citizens
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post is to announce the publication of a new paper: Operationalising Ecologically of Biologically Significant Marine Areas criteria for ecosystem-based conservation and management: The Bay of Biscay case https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1919357542330777723 https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3logc5q2jar2h	Researchers

CSIC	Communication	Social media	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post is to announce the publication of the new Barcelona's council blue school activities catalog where are published two activities related with MarinePlan project. https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1924497207027269932 https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3lpjxexg2l26	Citizens
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post is to announce the publication of the new paper: The opportunity for climate action through climate-smart Marine Spatial Planning. https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1925911706372313389 https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3lptrhb6ola22	Researchers
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post is to announce the publication of the new paper: Fishing activities within Spanish marine protected areas in the Mediterranean Sea https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1952265007351156810 https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3lvknhv3sdb25	Researchers
CSIC	Communication	Social media	Post in X (by the @iMARES_group profile) and BlueSky channel (by the @imares-group.bsky.social) .	The objective of the post is to announce the publication of the new poster: When the Sea Heats Up: Uneven Ecosystem Responses to Marine Heatwaves in the Western Mediterranean Sea for the EMBS2025 https://x.com/iMARES_group/status/1955651032505040928 https://bsky.app/profile/imares-group.bsky.social/post/3lwc4vvnhwb2u	Researchers
CSIC	Dissemination	Conferences	Attendance to International Conference MPA in MSP, in Bodo, Norway	Presentation a poster about W. Mediterranean EBSAs proposal based on key quantitative data.	Researchers
CSIC	Dissemination	Meetings	Presentation on the GFCM about MarinePlan and results from Western Mediterranean PS. Information considered by the subregional comitee of the Western Mediterranean	Oral presentation about the MarinePlan project and the results of the Western Mediterranean PS on the EBSAs, Scenarios and barriers and recommendations to enable a transboundary cooperation in MSP and MPA processes	Regional authorities
UNINA	Dissemination	Conferences	Attendance to the SER2025 Conference in Denver, United States (30th September - 4th October)	Oral communication on the outcomes of the Restoration Workshop (organized within task 3.2): "Marine restoration from a Marine Spatial Planning perspective".	Researchers
UNINA	Dissemination	Conferences	Attendance to International Conference MPA in MSP, in Bodo, Norway	Oral communication about connectivity the Campania MPAs.	Researchers

AZTI	Communication	Social media	Post in LinkedIn (by Ibon Galparsoro) announcing the MarinePlan final event	Inform about the final event to attract attendees	General audience
AZTI	Communication	Social media	Post in LinkedIn (by Ibon Galparsoro) announcing the MarinePlan final event	Inform about the final event to attract attendees	General audience
AZTI	Dissemination	Conferences	Attendance to the International Conference for YOUNG Marine Researchers (ICYMARE), Bremerhaven, Germany	Poster on Operationalising EBSA Criteria for Ecosystem-Based Conservation and Management. Oral communication on spatial conservation prioritisation scenarios in the Bay of Biscay	Researchers
AZTI	Dissemination	Conferences	Attendance to the ICES Annual Science Conference 2025, Klaipeda, Lithuania	Oral communication on spatial conservation prioritisation scenarios in the Bay of Biscay	Researchers
TI-SF	Dissemination	Conferences	Attendance at the MSP-Global Online Conference: 2.0 Closing & 3.0 Kick-off.	Panel Member presentation about: Thematic capacity development needs (Scenarios)	Researchers
AZTI	Dissemination	Other scientific collaboration	Publication of the EB-MSP assessment tool in the IOC-UNESCO/EC 2025 report.	UNESCO-IOC and European Commission. 2025. MSPglobal International Guide on Marine/Maritime Spatial Planning: Volume 2 – Biodiversity Inclusive Principle. Paris, UNESCO. (IOC Manuals and Guides No. 89, Volume 2). https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000395354	International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.)
AZTI	Dissemination	Conferences	Presentation at the Final MarinePlan Conference	Presentation about the EB-MSP assessment tool	Research communities
AZTI	Dissemination	Conferences	Presentation at the Final MarinePlan Conference	Training session on the EB-MSP assessment tool	Research communities
AZTI	Dissemination	Conferences	Presentation at the Final MarinePlan Conference	Presentation showcasing the Bay of Biscay results	Research communities
AZTI	Dissemination	Education and training events	Organization of an internal workshop with MarinePlan PS for operationalizing EBSAs	Technical workshop for standardizing the operationalization of EBSAs among Planning Sites	Research communities
UAEGEAN	Dissemination	Conferences	Presentation of the priorOECMs tool to the post International Congress for Conservation Biology 2025 Workshop on advancing OECMs, organised by Monash University, Brisbane, Australia, 20-21/6/2025	Presentation of the priorOECMs tool and its implementation in the 4 MarinePlan PS in the EU waters, aiming to develop an agenda to advance the implementation of OECMs	Research communities

UAEGEAN	Dissemination	Conferences	Oral presentation on Developing a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis Tool for Assessing Marine Areas as Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECMs) at the 60th meeting of the Estuarine & Coastal Sciences Association (ECSA), 2-5 September 2024, Hangzhou, China	Presentation of the Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis Tool for Assessing Marine Areas as OECMs in Session 2C: Human dimension-Challenges in the integration of ecological, socio-ecological and socio-economic aspects in estuarine, coastal and marine management & Community engagement and stakeholder involvement	Research communities
UAEGEAN	Dissemination	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Presentation of the priorOECMs tool to the INSPIRE project WS on Assessing Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECMs) under a Changing Climate	Presentation of the priorOECMs tool and its implementation in the 4 MarinePlan PS in the EU waters, to explore its extension to assess OECMs under a changing climate.	Research communities
UAEGEAN	Communication	Other	Dissemination of EB-MSP assessment results with national authorities	After completing the EB-MSP assessment, we shared the full results with the national authorities responsible for developing the country's MSP, following their request. These results will serve as a reference to inform and support the authorities in the MSP development process.	National authorities
QUB	Communication	Media article	A post on the EU MSP Platform website to promote participation in the surveys attached to each Planning Site's StoryMap.	The post helped to promote the surveys and provided a link that brought interested participants to the ArcGIS StoryMap for each Planning Site. The post can be accessed here - https://maritime-spatial-planning.ec.europa.eu/news/marineplan-survey-governance-ecosystem-based-marine-spatial-planning	Industry, business partners
QUB	Dissemination	Meetings	Oral presentation on network governance at a seminar organised by the Agri-Food and Biological Institute (AFBI).		Research communities
QUB	Dissemination	Conferences	Oral presentation on the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 EU conservation targets at the Ulster Wildlife 'Blue Horizons' conference, 20-21 January 2025, Belfast, UK		Research communities

QUB	Dissemination	Conferences	Oral presentation on the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 EU conservation targets at the Conference of Irish Geographers (CIG), 7-9 May 2025, Belfast, UK		Research communities
QUB	Dissemination	Conferences	Oral presentation on the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 EU conservation targets at the Maritime Research (MARE) Conference, 25-29 June 2025, Amsterdam, the Netherlands		Research communities
QUB	Dissemination	Conferences	Poster presentation at the Postdoc Showcase, held at Queen's University Belfast on 26th September 2025.	An opportunity to present findings and recommendations from WP4, particularly relating to other barriers and opportunities to achieving 30x30 conservation targets. The post can be viewed via the following link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183045	Research communities
QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in the Azores.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities
QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in the Bay of Biscay.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities
QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in Campania.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities

QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in the Celtic Sea.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities
QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in the Greek Aegean and Ionian Seas.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities
QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in the Southern North Sea.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities
QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in the Western Baltic Sea.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities
QUB	Dissemination	Other	Policy brief on how to foster Ecosystem-Based Marine Spatial Planning (EB-MSP) in the Western Mediterranean Sea.	This policy brief summarises some of the key findings relating to the barriers and enablers of achieving 30x30 conservation targets. This output was informed by work conducted in WP4, with additional input from other MarinePlan tasks. The document is designed as a means of clarifying the key issues, challenges and solutions that relate to marine governance decision-makers.	National authorities
TI	Dissemination	Conference	International Conference on Marine Protected Areas in Marine Spatial Planning (MPA in MSP). July 9-12, 2025, Bodø, Norway	Poster presentation on connectivity in MarinePlan project	Scientific Community
AZTI	Dissemination	Presentation	Ecosystem-based MSP Assessment tool: knowledge and guidance	Presentation at MarinePlan project final event. 29-30 September 2025. Online.	Scientific Community
AZTI	Dissemination	Presentation	Operationalising Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas (EBSA) criteria for ecosystem-based conservation and management	Presentation at MarinePlan project final event. 29-30 September 2025. Online.	Scientific Community